

Popular Article

Sexed semen technology a boon to the Dairy Industry

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Abstract

Livestock farmers always incline producing young ones of the desired sex, to meet the increasing demand for meat and milk which leads to economic benefits to the farmer. Earlier, various techniques have been employed to separate the X and Y sperm, some of the techniques showed encouraging results but lack scientific validation and some remained yet to be established. Presently only one, flow cytometry, is effective. However, the accuracy of the process is great but the speed and yield are slow and low. Additionally, equipment is extremely expensive, and specially trained technicians are required to assure sorting accuracy. Despite these limitations, sexed semen is being produced and cryopreserved for artificial insemination.

Introduction

The expanding demand for dairy products entails a greater focus on improving the dairy industry. Dairy farming is the major supportive business of the farmers in a rural area. There is about 192.49 million cattle population in India. Though artificial insemination increases the overall pregnancy rate, it does not give a choice to produce either male or female offspring. The advent of the sexed semen technology has brought a revolution in cattle breeding. This technology of sex determination prior to conception has always fascinated the reproductive biotechnologist. In the early 20th century, it became conspicuous that the male gamete determines the sex of offspring. However, success couldn't be achieved in sorting the X and Y chromosomes as all the sperms are phenotypically identical and no method was available for determining the composition of chromosomes in sperms before the last two decades. The evolution of the sex sorting technique of spermatozoa based on their DNA content with high accuracy proved an asset to the AI industry. Thus, integrating sexed semen into the breeding program can minimize the number of undesirable male dairy calves and also reduces the chances of dystocia. This technology is expected to come as a blessing for the farmers who prefer cows over bulls to enhance their dairy business in terms of productivity as well as profitability.

An attempt has been made to sort the X and Y-bearing spermatozoa but success was achieved only after the chemical composition of X and a Y-bearing spermatozoon was studied. The use of sex-sorted technique allows the predetermination of calf sex with 90% reliability.

In cattle, an X-chromosome bearing sperm contains 3.8% more DNA than a Y chromosome bearing sperm (Johnson, 1995), providing an attribute that can be utilized to differentiate between the sperm bearing X or Y chromosome. Different methods are available for sperm sorting which includes albumen gradient method, percoll density gradient method, swim-up procedure, free flow electrophoresis, identification of H-Y antigen, sorting based on volumetric differences, centrifugal counter current distribution, immunological approaches, and flow cytometry. Among this flow cytometry is commonly used for sorting of sperm.

Applications of sexed semen

The prime reason for consolidating sex-sorted semen in the dairy or beef system is to impose a desired sex bias in the resulting progeny. Herd replacements and additional heifers for herd expansion at a faster rate from within a herd; can be generated with the help of sexed semen, thereby reducing the biosecurity risk associated with bringing in animals from different herds. Sexed semen helps to increase the selection intensity by choosing superior females as replacements. For maintaining the constant herd strength for herd replacement 80% of females must be bred. By the application of sexed semen, a producer is required to breed only 40% of the cows for an equal number of herd replacements and therefore increase the selection intensity. In addition to this, the use of sexed semen can increase herd genetic gain compared with the use of conventional semen. Utilizing the sexed semen would minimize the production of unwanted male dairy breed calves, thus allaying potential welfare issues associated with it. Sexed semen reduces the incidence of dystocia and the risk factors associated with it like retained fetal membranes, uterine diseases, delayed resumption of estrous cyclicity and conception failures. The use of the sexed semen will reduce the number of destitute animals since the male calves; unproductive females are left for roaming on roads to reduce the financial burden, incurred by the farmers for management purposes.

Commercialization of sexed semen will help to increase the heifer calves either to expand or to sell replacements. However, if most heifer producers use this technology the cost of replacements is likely to come down substantially and thereby, making the heifer rearing system less profitable. In most of breeding programs incentives are often rewarded to the farmers for producing male calves. Through the use of sexed semen young bulls can be produced from the elite cows which can be successfully used for further breeding programs. For the conservation of endangered species sexed semen can prove beneficial, where any change in male and female sex ratios could lead to species extinction. It would also help in the optimization of breeding programs of zoo animals for avoiding inbreeding and to make long-term breeding plans. This

technology can also prove to be a powerful tool for studying the sex-limited and sex-influenced traits. It can be employed to study the sex-limited diseases as well as problems of infertility.

Limitations

There are some technological and implementation limitations associated with the sexed semen technology like the high cost of the sex-sorting machine, low sorting efficiency and speed, require a highly skilled person to operate the machine, damage to the sperm due to shear force, electrostatic charge, and droplet formation. There is wastage of approximately 50% of sperm during the sorting procedure. The sperm concentration in sexed semen is less as compared to the conventional semen straw. The sexing procedure poses injury to the sexed sperm; the conception rate is around 10 percent less with sexed semen as compared to conventional semen. However, with the advancement of technology and sexing equipment, the gap between sexed and conventional semen in terms of conception rate is lowering.

Current scenario

Currently in India 5 semen stations are producing sexed semen. And they are available at the rate of ₹ 900-2000 per dose however some states are making them available at a subsidized rate of ₹ 100-300. This sexed semen is not available in all the AITs. The breeds of cattle for which sexed semen is available in India include Gir, Sahiwal, Tharparkar, Kankrej, Red Sindhi, Hariana, Gangatiri, CBHF/CBJ, and pure HF and Jersey and buffalo Mehsana, Murrah, and Jaffarabadi. Taking into consideration the high fertility rate of the heifers, the recommendation is to use this semen only in the heifers (especially virgin heifers) for better a conception rate. However, the sex-sorted semen can be used in cows up to the third lactation with an excellent reproduction record.

Conclusion

The use of sexed semen can be of huge benevolence to society as it can address the problem of destitute animals and also greater genetic gain can be achieved through it. Also, the success of the sexed semen industry depends largely upon sorting speed, accuracy, and fertility of the sorted semen and existing technologies. Till date sex sorting through a flow cytometer is the only fully validated method for sperm sexing. Though this technique has some constraints on sexed semen quality, therefore several improvements have been recently made in sperm sorting procedures. In the future, it is possible to improve the existing methods or to develop an entirely new technology package for sorting spermatozoa and thus it needs to be researched further to achieve a greater good for society.

References

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